

**ADMINISTRATIVE PRACTICES AND THEIR INFLUENCE ON
TEACHER EFFECTIVENESS IN PUBLIC JUNIOR SECONDARY**

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Abstract: The study investigated Schools administrative obligational practices and teachers' job effectiveness in public junior secondary schools in Rivers State. The study adopted correlational design to find out relationship existing between the variables and inferences was drawn on data collected. The population for the study consists of eight thousand, three hundred and sixty-seven (8,367) teachers in public junior secondary schools. Simple random sampling technique was used to select a sample of 1,255 teachers' which represent 15% of the population. The instrument used was Administrative Obligational Practices and Teachers' Job Effectiveness Questionnaire (AOPTJEQ). The instrument was a four (4) point Likert scale and consisted of thirty (30) items. The reliability coefficients were 0.73 using Pearson Product Moment Correlation, three research questions guided the study and three hypotheses were postulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer research questions while regression analysis was used for data analysis. The findings revealed that there was a significant relationship between administrative obligational practices and teachers' job effectiveness. The significant relationship was seen between influence regular monitoring/evaluation on teachers,' influence of distributive leadership on teachers' and influence of provision of teaching facilities on teachers' job effectiveness. Premised on these findings recommendations that, monitoring and evaluation of school should be regularly carried out by Ministry of Education, school board, with the aim of improving teacher effectiveness. School administrators should adopt distributive leadership model to inculcate sense of responsibility among teachers' and government should provide school facilities that will help to facilitate learners understanding.

Keywords: School Administrative Obligational Practices, Teacher, Job, Effectiveness and Secondary Schools

INTRODUCTION

The teachers' place in the society is of vital need. He is the pivot for the transmission of intellectual traditions and technical skills from generation to generation and helps to keep the lamp of civilization burning. The teacher is the yardstick that measures the achievements and aspirations of any nation that values education. Based on these, teachers are the real nation builders. In striving for teachers' effectiveness and quality teaching learning outcomes, there are many factors that are imperative in the process. Factors, such as school leadership, management

approach, school plant utilization and teachers involvement in decision making in the school are prerequisite for successful school administration.

The quality of learning environment is crucial in raising educational standard and teacher effectiveness. The environment embodies physical, psychosocial and service delivery elements. The physical elements have to do with quality of school facilities such as classroom, library, laboratory, mechanical tool, plumber and ICT and classroom management which entails arrangement of seats, how ventilated the classroom is, number of students per-class, the size of classroom, position of white or black board, location of the classroom which are correlated with students achievement sometimes, this achievement is used to measure teacher effectiveness .so these facilities must meet up standard in order to enhance effective and efficient teaching . Effective school administration has a key role in enhancing teacher effectiveness because administrator is the mediator which has the authority to develop and empower teachers in the quest of school effectiveness. Proactive administration is a life wire for efficient and effectiveness in every goal-oriented organization which school is one of them. In order to achieve teacher effectiveness, administrators has a central role to ensure and maintain the school improvement which has to do with the quality of teaching. The school head must embrace the different leadership styles in order to face administrative challenge and assist the teachers to carry out effective teaching and learning without clamoring in their duty schedules.

Among other vital factors is teacher preparation and quality which is an inevitable factor that determines learner performance and achievement. Effective teaching and learning are as a result of adequate preparation and planning, if teacher lacks behind in planning, it means that poor performance will be observed in the instructional delivery and the specific lesson objective will not be achieved. The preparation of teacher boosts his confidence in handling classroom management, improvisation skills, time management and suitable selection of activities that will tally with the specific learning objectives in line with scheme of work. To be an effective teacher is never accidental, for a teacher to Impact meaningful lesson to students. The teacher requires a lesson plan that is thoughtfully planned and prepared regardless of his or her ability, experience and field of training. It is necessary for teachers to prepare their lessons on a daily basis beforehand and implement using the most appropriate teaching methods. Teacher attending classroom without adequate preparation of lesson plan will not only frustrate the teacher but mislead learners with wrong notion of teaching, which will create the impression of unprofessional and incompetent of the teacher.

The rationale behind lesson plan is to serve as a guide that teachers used every day to determine what the students will learn, how the lesson will be taught, as well x-ray how learning will be evaluated. For good lesson plans enables teachers to function more effectively in the classroom by giving the nitty-gritty of steps outlined that the teacher adheres to during class session. This helps to manage time in the classroom for teaching meaningful concepts.

The prudent utilization of equipment and other classroom material cannot be neglected in the quest of teacher effectiveness. Most times teachers underutilize teaching materials there by making teaching ineffective. The delivery of quality instruction in the classroom in any education system depends mainly on the quality and competence of the teachers in handling instructional equipment that enhance teaching and learning.

This is so because lesson appears abstract and boring when relevant teaching aids or instructional materials are not used to concretize the lesson, the students see lesson to be theoretical instead of practical and activity-based lesson. The proper use of equipment during teaching draws learners' attention and sustained interest which in turn create pictorial imagination during and after lesson period.

Teacher welfare and motivation is a determinant factor to enhance teacher performance in the discharge of their multifarious responsibilities. Effectiveness in teaching will remain an educational mirage if teachers' welfare and

motivation is ignored. Welfare is it at the micro level of a school or large society is a critical index used in determining the degree of commitment to social, psychological well-being of workers (teacher) who strive for optimal performance in the educational system. In every education system low morale and poor motivation will often lead to poor performance and ineffectiveness in teaching and learning, the brain-drain of teachers' in public secondary schools in Nigeria to other lucrative jobs may not be far from poor condition of service in the teaching profession, teacher welfare and motivation still remain the hub of encouragement that will propel teacher for continuous quest for effectiveness in teaching and learning without much monitoring and supervision moreover, high remuneration allowance and other staff benefits will grease their elbow but in addition providing opportunities to benefits from their mistakes rather than get irritated and shout at teacher for making mistake will try to redirect the way they think about their teaching, the school administrator should use to better appraise the teachers' intention which in turn make them more effective in instructional delivery .

Among all the multifarious factors that enhance teacher effectiveness, the survival of any organization especially education is dependent on the quality of administrative and management services available. Monitoring of school is an important observational technique that regularly place educational activities in a prescribed pathway. The monitoring visits by relevant stakeholders of education helps to give advice and feedback to improve quality standardize policy. The main purpose of monitoring activity is to collect data that will inform and facilitate improvement in classroom practice. Monitoring in the school system is checking if the school academic and nonacademic staff are doing what they are trained and assigned to do, in a systematic approach to overseeing planning, learning and teaching. Monitoring is not result yielding exercise without evaluation, therefore monitoring and evaluation is the process of gathering information in order to make judgment and suggest the further ways of improvement. Evaluating on its own is the measurements of success. This is done after there is a comparison between outcomes, aims and objectives. This eventually leads to a summative assessment of current practices within the school, then informs on the future planning for both learning and teaching. School monitoring and evaluation help in providing a consolidated source of information showing the progress of the school. Monitoring and evaluation as strategies are important for accountability, performance and planning which in return lead to school improvement through teacher effectiveness.

Statement of the Problem

The productivity of every organization is solely dependent on administrative functions of the head, whose functions includes planning, staffing, coordinating, organizing, controlling, supervising, directing and using human and material resources to achieve the goals of the organization. In the case of Universal Basic Education, parents and guardians of learners are lamenting on the declined performance of students in basic education system which have displayed its self in students' inability to read, poor communication skills, poor calligraphic skills and mass failure in their Basic Junior secondary school examines. In order to improve the basic education in Nigeria, the federal and state government made basic education officially free and compulsory. To assure there is quality education, the government has put in place renowned educational projects and policy like free feeding, provision of furnished classroom blocks, quality supply of instructional materials, recruitment of professional teachers' and continuous professional development program for teachers to update their knowledge and instructional competency yet there is outcry from the public about low quality of education. Also considering the input made, teacher effectiveness supposed to be recommendable but the society still point fingers at teachers not doing their works effectively. This disparity is attributed to teachers' ineffectiveness, nonchalant attitude of the school administration and the supervisory functions from of school heads. Despite the regular supervision of schools with the intention of improving education through the use of supervision, monitoring and school evaluation yet there is a claim that teachers could not perform their duties effectively. It is against this background that this study

sought to examine administrative obligation practices and teachers' job effectiveness in public junior secondary schools in Rivers State with a view to proffer working solution.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study examined the relationship between administrative obligations practices and teachers' job effectiveness in public junior secondary schools in Rivers State, the study specifically sought to:

1. Examine the extent regular evaluation and monitoring of schools influence teachers' job effectiveness in public junior secondary schools in Rivers State.
2. Assess the extent distributive leadership in schools influence teachers' job effectiveness in public junior secondary schools in Rivers State.
3. Determine the extent provision of teaching facilities influence teachers' job effectiveness in public junior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated and guided this study:

1. To what extent does regular monitoring and evaluation of school influence teachers' effectiveness in public junior secondary schools in Rivers state?
2. To what extent does distributive leadership in school influence teachers' job effectiveness in public junior secondary schools in Rivers State?
3. To what extent does provision of teaching facilities influence teachers' job effectiveness in public junior secondary schools in Rivers state?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were postulated to guide the study and were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

Ho₁: There is no significant relationship between regular monitoring and evaluation of school and teachers' job effectiveness in public junior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Ho₂: There is no significant relationship between distributive leadership in school and teachers' job effectiveness in public junior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Ho₃: There is no significant relationship between provision of teaching facilities and teachers' job effectiveness in public junior secondary schools in Rivers State.

METHODOLOGY

This study examined the relationship between Administrative Obligations Practices and Teachers' job effectiveness in public junior secondary schools in Rivers State. This study therefore adopted the correlational design. This design is regarded appropriate because it examined the relationship between Administrative Obligations Practices and Teacher Job effectiveness. The information gathered through the use of questionnaire was analyzed using the appropriate data analysis.

The population of this study comprised all the teachers in public junior secondary school in Rivers State. The teachers' population in public junior secondary school is 8,367 (RSUBEB 2018/2019). The teachers were also being used as respondents.

The simple random sampling technique was adopted to select 15% of the teachers' drawn from the targeted population of 8,367. This approximately gave 1,255 teachers. This constitutes the research sample.

The instrument used for this study was a questionnaire. The first part of the questionnaire was used to generate demographic information while the second part address Administrative Obligations Practices and Teacher Job Effectiveness Questionnaire (AOPTJEQ). The second part of the instrument was structured on the modified 4 points Likert scale of Very High Extent (VHE) High Extent (HE) Low Extent (LE) Very Low Extent (VLE).

The research instrument was administered by the researcher to the teachers in the public junior secondary schools through a research assistant. One thousand two hundred and fifty-five (1,255) questionnaires were administered to the teachers' and one thousand twenty (1,020) questionnaires were retrieved due to some errors from the respondents. The returned instruments were used in the analysis of data.

The response on the items of the instrument were collated and analyzed. The mean and standard deviation of the responses to each item were used to analyze and answered the research question, while simple regression analysis of SPSS was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Presentation of Result

Research Question One: To what extent does regular monitoring/evaluation influence teachers' job effectiveness of public junior secondary schools in Rivers State?

Table 1: Mean responses on the extent regular monitoring/evaluation influenced teacher job effectiveness of public junior secondary schools in Rivers State N=1,020; Criterion Mean=2.50

S/N	Regular monitoring/evaluation	Mean	Std	Remark
11	Regular evaluation and monitoring helps to place teachers on watch which in turn brings improvement in instructional delivery.	3.84	0.54	High Extent
12	Regular evaluation and monitoring helps to monitor the progress of school which in turn suggest further ways for school advancement.	3.67	0.77	High Extent
13	Regular evaluation and monitoring assist in checking the implementation of curriculum which in turn brings feedback to policy maker.	3.38	0.78	High Extent
14	Regular evaluation and monitoring facilitates whole school evaluation (WSE) which in turn aid in data collection and analysis.	3.78	0.48	High Extent
15	Regular evaluation and monitoring helps to monitor the teachers' class attendance which in turn aid teachers in syllabus coverage.	3.76	0.51	High Extent
Grand Mean		3.69	0.62	High Extent

Sources: SPSS output, 2025

Table 1 above showed the mean and standard deviation on the extent regular monitoring /evaluation influence teachers' job effectiveness of public junior secondary schools in Rivers State. The data in the table showed that respondents indicated that regular monitoring/evaluation influenced teachers' job effectiveness of public junior secondary schools in Rivers State to a high extent (Mean=3.69, Std=0.62). The respondents indicated that Regular evaluation and monitoring helps to place teachers on watch which in turn brings improvement in instructional delivery of public junior secondary schools in Rivers State to the highest extent (Mean=3.84, Std=0.54).

Research Question Two: To what extent does distributive leadership model influence teachers’ job effectiveness of public junior secondary schools in Rivers State? **Table 2: Mean responses on the extent distributive leadership influenced teachers’ job effectiveness of public junior secondary schools in Rivers State N=1,020; Criterion Mean=2.50**

S/N	Distributive leadership and teachers’ job effectiveness	Mean	Std	Remark
21	Distributive leader helps to inculcate sense of responsibility among teachers.	3.79	0.52	High Extent
22	Distributive leadership enhances the achievement of school goals through sharing of duties among school personnel.	3.66	0.55	High Extent
23	Distributive leadership encourages the participatory of teachers in decision making.	3.86	0.44	High Extent
24	Distributive leadership helps to facilitate activities in the school even in the absent of school leader.	3.80	0.42	High Extent
25	Distributive leadership encourages the involvement of role partners in school management which in turn promote team work.	3.74	0.68	High Extent
Grand Mean		3.77	0.52	High Extent

Sources: SPSS output, 2025

Table 2 above showed the mean and standard deviation on the extent distributive leadership influence teachers job effectiveness of public junior secondary schools in Rivers State. The data in the table showed that respondents indicated that distributive leadership influences teachers’ job effectiveness of public junior secondary schools in Rivers State to a high extent (Mean=3.77, Std=0.52). The respondents indicated that distributive leadership encourages the participatory of teachers’ in decision making in public junior secondary schools in Rivers State to the highest extent (Mean=3.86, Std=0.44).

Research Question Three: To what extent does provision of school facilities influence teachers’ job effectiveness of public junior secondary schools in Rivers State?

Table 3: Mean responses on the extent provision of school facilities influenced teachers’ job effectiveness of public junior secondary schools in Rivers State N=1,020; Criterion Mean=2.50

S/N	Provision of school facilities and teacher job effectiveness	Mean	Std	Remark
26	Provision of school equipment in instructional delivery help to concretize lessons which in turn boost teachers’ result.	3.84	0.54	High Extent
27	Provision of instruction materials helps to facilitate learners understanding through effective application.	3.67	0.77	High Extent
28	Provision of school facilities motivate teachers’ job performance.	3.38	0.78	High Extent
29	Provision of teaching apparatus for teachers’ and learners encourages hands-on and mind-on activities in classroom.	3.78	0.48	High Extent
30	Provision of school facilities helps to arouse the interest of the learner which in turn increase teachers’ productivity.	3.76	0.51	High Extent
Grand Mean		3.69	0.62	High Extent

Sources: SPSS output, 2025

Table 3 above showed the mean and standard deviation on the extent provision of school facilities influence teachers’ job effectiveness of public junior secondary schools in Rivers State. The data in the table showed that respondents indicated that provision of school facilities influences teachers’ job effectiveness of public junior secondary schools in Rivers State to a high extent (Mean=3.69, Std=0.62). The respondents indicated that Provision of school equipment in instructional delivery help to concretize lessons which in turn boost teachers’ result in public junior secondary schools in Rivers State to the highest extent (Mean=3.84, Std=0.54).

Discussion of Findings

The results from the respondents revealed that regular monitoring and evaluation helps to place teachers’ on watch which in turn brings improvement in instructional delivery, regular evaluation and monitoring helps to monitor the progress of school which in turn suggest further way for school advancement, regular evaluation and monitoring assist in checking the implementation of curriculum which in turn brings feedback to policy maker in education, regular evaluation and monitoring helps to monitor the teachers’ class attendance which in turn aid teachers’ in syllabus coverage which is attributed to teacher job effectiveness in public junior secondary schools in

Rivers State. This is made known in the significant level of .000 and a t-value of 29.778. This means that there is significant relationship between monitoring/evaluation and teachers’ job effectiveness in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

This result is in line with Namfukwe. (2016), opined that monitoring and evaluation influences school performance of upper primary teachers’ towards improving teaching and learning. He went further to assert that teachers’ understood monitoring and evaluation as evidenced through acceptance of advice for making

improvement in their job performance. In agreement to the finding, Ibrahim (2020) affirmed that monitoring of teachers on their reporting on duty and leaving from duty improved the teachers' and learners in schools are completing the syllabus coverage in time. Also, the in consonant to the finding, Vipene, and Kerene, (2021) viewed that monitoring is aimed at the improving efficiency and effectiveness, assisting with keeping work on target and permitting the executives to know when things are turning out bad, enabling organizations to find out if resources available are sufficient and being well utilized, finding out if capacity available is sufficient and appropriate, finally giving helpful base for evaluation. Therefore, evaluation of teaching process involves collecting evidence from various stakeholders for the purpose of improving the effectiveness of the teaching learning process for optimum performance of both the teachers' and learners. Also, the findings are reflected by Fullan (2011) who asserted that evaluation is a task which has its purpose in identification of merits and deficiencies and it is an integrative part of the control task. The finding is supported by D Souza (2016) who noted that evaluation is a useful means of determining whether a person has carried out his given task, whether a person is helping to achieve set objectives and to determine when a specific person with his unique qualities and specific talents give the best service. Assuming that no one is perfect and therefore everyone has room for improvement, evaluation is the means which teachers' try to identify which aspect of their teaching is good which one needs to be changed (Fullan, 2011).

Distributive leader helps to inculcate sense of responsibility among teachers', distributive leadership enhances the achievement of school goals through sharing of duties among school personnel, distributive leadership encourages the participatory of teachers in decision making, distributive leadership helps to facilitate activities in the school even in the absent of school leader. Distributive leadership encourages the involvement of role partners in school management which in turn promote team work and as well increases teachers' job effectiveness in public junior secondary schools in Rivers State. This means that there is significant relationship between distributive leadership and teachers' job effectiveness in public junior secondary schools in Rivers State.

The above findings agree with those of earlier studies like Loeser, (2008), Ibara, (2011) Botha, & Marishane, (2011) studies revealed that the purpose of distributed leadership is to bring the school management team and other teachers in contact with the goals and values of the school. They also affirm that distributed leadership relieves the principal of the many responsibilities of administration and other school activities. Furthermore, it makes teachers' to collectively assume responsibility for the wellbeing of their schools. In the same vein, Botha (2014) asserted that the distribution of leadership has important effect on enhancing teacher commitment and involvement in decision making. This is achieved by involving more teachers in leadership responsibilities in the school system leading to generation of innovations with a strong team approach. House and Aditja in Ibara (2011) described distributed leadership as the process of leadership which involves collaborative relationships that lead to collective action anchored on the shared value of people who work together to bring about positive change. In support of the finding, Leithwood and Reid (2003) affirmed that distributed leadership ensures that teachers' and principals work together towards the attainment of school goals. To buttress the concept distributed leadership, MacBeath (2005) saw distributed leadership as an ability to relinquish one's role as ultimate decision maker, trusting others to make the right decisions and a brief in the potential and authority of others.

In consonant to this finding, Ibara (2011) asserted that the application of distributed leadership model improves instructional programs in secondary schools administration, promotes acquisitions of new knowledge, enhances interaction with staff, improve students' learning outcome, assist teachers improve their job performance and opening up opportunities for teachers' career development which in turn brings teachers' bob effectiveness. The findings are in line with David and Gamage in Mbogori (2012) who noted that effective participatory or shared

leadership in school administration influence the trust of students by reducing unfaithfulness, grudges and indiscipline.

Provision of school equipment in instructional delivery help to concretize lessons which in turn boost teachers' result, provision of instructional materials helps to facilitate learners understanding through effective application, Provision of school facilities motivate teachers' job performance, provision of teaching apparatus for teachers' and learners encourages hands-on and mind-on activities in classroom, Provision of school facilities helps to arouse the interest of the learner which in turn increase teachers' productivity which are accounted for teachers' job effectiveness in public junior secondary schools in Rivers state. This means that there is significant relationship between provision of school facilities and teachers' job effectiveness in public junior secondary schools in Rivers State.

In consonant to this finding, Ojeritude, (2019) asserted that provision of necessary facilities in schools will enrich and make the school an enabling environment for teaching and learning. He went further to opine that any school suitable for academic work requires physical facilities such as well constructed and equipped classroom furniture, games facilities, laboratories and hostels with basic amenities and other equipment necessary for teaching and learning. Fabunmi in Usen (2016) supported this finding by asserting that school facilities when provided will aid teaching learning programme and consequently improve academic achievement of students while the models guiding their provision to schools could take any form as rational bureaucratic or political model.

In the same vein, Baloguncited in David (2015) submitted that no effective science programme can exist without equipment for teaching. This is because facilities enable the learner and teachers to develop problem solving skills and scientific attitudes. In corroborate with the findings, Ajayi and Ogunyemi in Eliasu et al. (2016) affirmed that when facilities are provided to meet relative needs of a school system, students will not only have access to the reference materials mentioned by the teacher, but individual students will also be learning at their own paces. The net effect of this, school facility increased job performance of the teacher and students' outcome. Other scholars like (Wilcockson,, Lawal, Ajayi, Suleiman 2020) supported the findings by identifying the significance of facilities in teaching and learning spheres. This is in line with Maphosa and Shumba (2010) and Dominic et al (2017) reveals that most of the public secondary schools with adequate school facilities such as classrooms, school library with relevant books, science laboratories with apparatus and chemicals and sports ground can be said to have a healthy school climate which may lead to high levels of students' discipline and with that its influence the school effectiveness. Also Olanrewaju et., al. (2020) supported the finding by affirming that physical facilities planning had a positive and significant relationship with school effectiveness in Kwara State public secondary schools. This implies that physical facilities planning will go a long way in improving educational standard, school effectiveness as well as students' academic performance in Kwara State public secondary schools.

Conclusion

The study examined Administrative obligations practices and teachers' job effectiveness in junior secondary schools in Rivers State. Based on the result of the findings the study concludes that there is a significant relationship between administrative obligation practices and teachers' job effectiveness in public junior secondary schools. The study has established that regular monitoring and evaluation influence teachers' job effectiveness, distributive leadership on schools promote synergetic performance among teachers' and provision of school facilities enhance teachers' effectiveness of public secondary schools in Rivers State to a high extent. The study also revealed that regular monitoring and evaluation helps to place teachers' on watch which in turn brings improvement in instructional delivery, regular monitoring and evaluation helps to monitor the progress of school, regular monitoring/evaluation assists in checking the implementation of curriculum which in turn brings feedback to policy maker, regular monitoring/evaluation facilitation whole school evaluation which aid in data collection

and analysis, regular monitoring/evaluation helps to monitor the teachers' class attendance. Further, the study revealed that distributive leadership helps to inculcate sense of responsibility among teachers', distributive leadership enhances the achievement of school goals through sharing of duties among school personnel distributive leadership encourages the participatory of teachers' in decision making, distributive leadership helps to facilitate activities in the school even in the absent of school leader and distributive leadership encourages the involvement of role partners in school management which in turn promote team work.

The study went further to revealed that provision of school equipment helps to concretize lesson, provision of instructional materials helps to facilitate learners understanding through effective application, job performance, provision of teaching apparatus for teachers' and learners encourages hands on and mind-on activities in classroom and provision of school facilities helps to arouse the interest of the learner which in turn increase teachers' productivity.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Monitoring and evaluation of schools as an administrative obligations should be regularly carried out by ministry of education, school board, zonal board and administrators with the aim of improving teacher effectiveness and school appraisal.
2. School administrators should adopt distributive leadership approach to inculcate sense of responsibility among teachers.
3. Government should provide school equipment that will help to facilitate learners understanding through effective application.

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